

Martin et al.: REPRODUCTIVE TRACT SIZE AND POSITION

Supplementary Table S2. Posterior mean, posterior standard deviation (PSD) and highest posterior density (HPD) interval of the heritability estimates resulting from the bivariate models between the reproductive size and position score and other currently evaluated traits, estimated on records from 490 Holstein cows over three years in one herd, in comparison to the heritability estimates from the literature*.

Trait	Bivariate analysis			Literature*
	Posterior mean (\pm PSD)	Low HPD	High HPD	Posterior mean (\pm PSD)
CONFORMATION				
Body Condition Score	0.323 (\pm 0.055)	0.228	0.406	0.227 (\pm 0.003)
Thurl Placement	0.153 (\pm 0.004)	0.088	0.220	0.227 (\pm 0.003)
Rump Angle	0.250 (\pm 0.045)	0.172	0.322	0.362 (\pm 0.002)
PRODUCTION				
Milk Yield	0.341 (\pm 0.051)	0.260	0.423	0.306 (\pm 0.001)
Protein Yield	0.223 (\pm 0.044)	0.145	0.290	0.215 (\pm 0.001)
Fat Yield	0.215 (\pm 0.039)	0.146	0.277	0.285 (\pm 0.001)
FERTILITY				
Age at First Service	0.031 (\pm 0.018)	0.005	0.057	0.045 (\pm 0.001)
Non-Return Rate At 56 Days	0.058 (\pm 0.017)	0.029	0.082	0.015 (\pm 0.001)
First Service to Conception	0.159 (\pm 0.034)	0.109	0.215	0.031 (\pm 0.001)
Calving to First Service	0.049 (\pm 0.019)	0.019	0.078	0.060 (\pm 0.001)
Days Open	0.009 (\pm 0.004)	0.003	0.014	0.066 (\pm 0.002)
Number of Services	0.181 (\pm 0.027)	0.138	0.226	0.033 (\pm 0.001)
CALVING				
Calving Ease	0.025 (\pm 0.010)	0.009	0.040	0.029 (\pm 0.001)

*Heritability estimates of the traits for the Canadian Holstein population presented in Oliveira Junior et al. (2021).